

Enhancing IoT Network Lifetime Using Mobility-Aware Clustering and Multi-Hop Routing with a Data Collection Node in WSNs

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Abstract:

The Internet of Things (IoT) connects billions of devices globally, enabling real-time data sharing and remote operations. However, energy constraints and mobility in IoT nodes pose challenges, particularly in maintaining network lifetime. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), the foundation of IoT, demand efficient, scalable, and energy-aware solutions. This study proposes two approaches to prolong IoT network lifespan. First, a Mobility-Aware Weighted Clustering Algorithm (MAWCA) selects optimal cluster

Keywords: *Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), Internet of Things(IoT), Mobility-Aware Weighted Clustering Algorithm (MAWCA), Energy-Aware and Secure Multi-Hop Routing (ESMR) protocol, DCnode and Cloud-Assisted IoT.*

1 INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) connects billions of devices, enabling remote monitoring and control. These devices generate massive volumes of data, requiring energy-efficient data routing for sustainable operation. However, battery limitations and node mobility in IoT networks reduce network lifetime, making Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) a critical infrastructure for managing energy-constrained devices.

In WSNs, data is transmitted from sensor nodes to the sink via either direct or cluster-based multi-hop routing. Clustering improves energy usage by aggregating data at a Cluster Head (CH) before transmission. Yet, static CHs face high energy depletion. Thus,

heads based on routing energy, outperforming existing methods like the Multi-objective Fractional Gravitational Search Algorithm. Second, a Data Collection Node (DC node) integrated with a Cloud-Assisted IoT algorithm is used to aggregate sparse data and improve transmission efficiency through clustering. Cloud-based device awareness enhances routing and decision-making in heterogeneous IoT networks.

efficient clustering and routing algorithms are necessary to improve energy efficiency, scalability, and network longevity.

1.1 Wireless Sensor Networks and IoT Integration

WSNs consist of sensors that monitor physical parameters and send data to base stations. They are widely used in applications like agriculture, healthcare, environmental monitoring, and smart cities. However, WSN nodes are resource-constrained in terms of power, memory, and communication range.

With IoT integration, WSNs can be accessed globally but face issues such as security, addressing, and resource management. Thus, IoT-WSN integration requires intelligent, scalable architectures that address topology, routing, and energy efficiency.

1.2 Key Design Challenges in WSNs

Energy consumption: Limited battery life demands low-energy protocols.

Error tolerance: Nodes may fail due to harsh environments.

Scalability: Networks may consist of hundreds or thousands of nodes.

Topology management: Requires efficient layout for reduced energy use.

Routing efficiency: Needs optimal CH selection and robust multi-hop paths.

1.3 IoT and Its Importance

IoT connects physical objects to the internet, enabling automation, data analytics, and real-time decision-making. Devices range from smartphones to industrial machinery. IoT systems rely on sensors, network connectivity, and cloud-based analytics to function efficiently. They improve energy use, monitor utilities, and support applications such as smart cities, precision farming, and transportation.

1.4 WSN Protocols and Clustering Techniques

WSN protocols span layers from physical to transport, enabling reliable data transmission under resource constraints. Routing protocols can be single-hop or multi-hop and are designed for data-centric, hierarchical, location-based, or QoS-aware needs. Clustering protocols improve scalability by organizing nodes into groups with CHs, reducing communication cost and balancing energy load.

2 RELATED WORKS

Recent advancements in energy-efficient clustering and routing protocols have significantly contributed to extending the lifespan of wireless sensor networks (WSNs). For instance, Yongcheng Wang (2022) introduced the Enhanced Multitier Energy-Efficient Clustering Protocol for IoT (EMEECP-IOT), tailored for heterogeneous

WSNs linked to IoT systems. By evaluating parameters such as network stability, received packets, throughput, and residual energy, simulation results revealed a 35% improvement in network longevity and a 21% reduction in energy consumption compared to conventional protocols, making it particularly valuable for IoT-based applications.

R. Prema et al. proposed the Secured Power-Aware and Energy-Efficient Routing Protocol (SPAERP) in 2013, which incorporates a novel cryptosystem alongside adaptive transmission power and routing strategies. Simulations using NS2 demonstrated SPAERP's ability to enhance Quality of Service (QoS) while minimizing energy usage. The protocol's cryptosystem was validated for security using Cryptool.

Similarly, Muhammad Bilal et al. (2022) presented a distributed clustering and routing system that emphasizes battery health. By using a charge utility metric during cluster formation, their approach optimized energy usage and extended network lifetime significantly compared to existing methods. This study underscored the importance of battery-aware design in improving the efficiency and longevity of WSNs.

In 2022, Subha R. and Anandakumar H. proposed the Improved Emperor Penguin Optimization Algorithm-Based Clustering Protocol (IEPOACP). By mimicking emperor penguins' huddling behavior, this protocol identified optimal cluster heads, resulting in a 67% increase in network lifespan, improved throughput, reduced latency, and better packet delivery rates compared to traditional methods.

Salim El Khediri et al. (2021) extended the TEEN protocol by introducing WB-TEEN and WBM-TEEN, which incorporated multi-

hop intra-cluster communication. These enhancements balanced node distribution and reduced energy consumption, achieving a 40% improvement in network lifespan compared to TEEN and LEACH protocols.

R. Prema et al. also proposed the Secured Power-Aware Routing Protocol (SPARP), which dynamically adjusts transmission power and incorporates a novel cryptosystem to enhance QoS while reducing energy costs. Simulations validated its ability to improve packet delivery ratios and reduce latency.

Lastly, Priyadarsini et al. introduced a source node-based routing method that eliminates repetitive routing information exchanges, optimizing network performance.

3 PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This study proposes two methods to extend IoT network lifetime. The first uses mobile nodes to enhance energy efficiency and secure multi-hop data transfer, compared to the multi-objective fractional gravitational search algorithm. The second integrates a data collection node with a mobility-aware weighted clustering algorithm to efficiently route sparse data. Simulations using NS2 demonstrate the results, with outputs visualized through NAM and X-Graph tools.

3.1 FIRST APPROACH OF THE PROPOSED WORK

3.1.1 CLUSTERING

Wireless sensor networks rely on battery-powered sensors with limited energy reserves. As a result, one of the primary objectives of WSN applications is to extend the network's lifespan. Clustering techniques have proven particularly effective in improving network performance by organizing sensor nodes into groups, optimizing resource utilization, and enhancing energy efficiency [9]. These methods are instrumental in overcoming the

constraints of limited energy, thereby prolonging the network's operational life.

3.1.2 ROUTING

Routing is a critical aspect of WSNs, particularly for prolonging the lifespan of sensor nodes. Numerous techniques have been proposed to optimize energy consumption and enhance network longevity [10]. This study focuses on routing strategies that integrate mobility-aware clustering and energy-efficient secure multi-hop routing to achieve significant improvements in network lifespan

3.1.3 PROPOSED PROTOCOL

This paper proposes the Mobility-Aware Weighted Clustering Algorithm (MAWCA) to select optimal cluster heads in mobile IoT networks by evaluating factors like degree difference, neighbor discrepancies, cumulative time, mobility, and delay. It integrates the Energy-Aware Secure Multi-Hop Routing (ESMR) protocol with secret sharing to enhance energy efficiency and data security. The approach offers a lightweight solution for multi-hop data routing in resource-constrained IoT-based wireless sensor networks.

3.1.4 STEPS INVOLVED IN COMPARING MAWCA & MOFGSA STEP 1 - INITIAL NODE DEPLOYMENT AND VISUALIZATION

Figure 3.1 illustrates the initial deployment of nodes within the simulation environment. Users are represented as green circles, with the source and destination nodes marked as blue hexagons. Cluster heads (CH1, CH2, CH3) are identified and displayed for efficient data communication. This visualization enables a clear understanding of node distribution and CH positioning.

Figure 3.1 Routing (NAM Animation tool)

STEP 2 - FORMATION OF CLUSTERS

In Figure 3.2, the clustering process begins with the selection of the source node, represented as a violet circle. This node initiates the clustering process by broadcasting messages to nearby nodes. Clusters form around CHs, aiming to minimize data loss before transmission. Small dots near the source node signify the initial phases of data exchange, indicating active communication links.

Figure 3.2 Formation of cluster

STEP 3 - PATH OPTIMIZATION FOR ROUTING

The routing protocol identifies the most efficient paths for data transmission. As depicted in Figure 3.3, paths between nodes are established to ensure minimal energy consumption. For example, the route includes nodes 0, 3, 8, 11, 12, 16, and 24, forming an optimal chain for packet delivery. Distance between nodes is minimized to improve overall efficiency.

Figure 3.3 Routing protocol

STEP 4 - MONITORING AND DATA SEGMENTATION

Cluster heads actively monitor data transfer within their clusters. As shown in Figure 3.4, nodes moving out of range are detected, and CHs adjust their communication strategies accordingly. For instance, node 7 transmits data packets segmented into smaller units to maintain communication reliability. Key performance metrics, such as transmission duration (5.73 seconds) and bit rate (111), are recorded in a ".tr" trace file.

Figure 3.4 Checking the data Information

STEP 5 - COMPLETE ROUTING AND VERIFICATION

The entire routing process is completed, as shown in Figure 3.5. Nodes such as 7 and 25 are highlighted in the routing path leading to the destination node (node 4). This step includes sending route requests, verifying thresholds, and receiving route replies to ensure the secure and efficient

transfer of data packets. This comprehensive routing approach enhances reliability and minimizes packet loss.

Figure 3.5 Path of Routing

3.2 SECOND APPROACH OF THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

3.2.1 STEPS INVOLVED IN COMPARING MAWCA & CA-IOT

STEP 1 - INITIAL NODE DEPLOYMENT AND VISUALIZATION

The advanced nodes are shown in figure 3.1 as AN1, AN2,... AN N in the red-ringed hexagon, with the cluster head and gateway also shown by blue double circles and green circles, respectively. At this stage, the user has been deployed.

Figure 3.1 Initial Stage

STEP 2 - DATA COLLECTION NODE

At this point, our proposed data gathering node has been implemented. Our additional work represents DC such as DC1, DC2 and so on.. where this node gathers the tiny range of data among the region and sends that to destination across the short distance by approaching nearby cluster head which is analysis by itself. Figure 3.2 depicts this as an orange circle.

Figure 3.2 Data collection node

STEP 3 - DATA INFORMATION

Figure 3.3 shows that we are getting information about the data, including its size (532 bytes). Since data cannot be sent as a single packet before being transformed into bytes, it must first be split into packets. It is for this reason that the data size is displayed above in bytes, that the transmission time is 5.73 seconds, and that the constant bit rate is 111. The output that was previously saved as ".tr," where ".tr" stands for "trace," is used to store the output. It was all stored in the file, from start to finish. One would anticipate the

preserved value to be an output.

Figure 3.3 Data information

STEP 4 - CHANGE IN DC NODE LOCATION

As time passes, the location of the data collection node changes. It changes its location at random, as seen in figure 3.9, and the final effect may be achieved using either the x-graph technique or the nam animation tool, as seen in the output simulation above.

Figure 3.4 Change in DC node Location

4 SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION AND CODINGS

4.1 NS-2 Software

Network Simulator 2 (NS2) is an event-driven simulation tool specifically designed to study the dynamics of communication networks. It provides extensive support for modeling both wired and wireless network technologies, enabling

the simulation of routing methods, transport protocols like TCP and UDP, and other network behaviors.

The architecture of NS2 is divided into two primary components: C++ for backend operations and OTcl (Object Tool Command Language) for frontend tasks. The interface between these components is facilitated by TclCL, which enables smooth communication and functionality across the two layers.

NS2 employs a simulation script written in Tcl as input, which is executed using the command "ns." The simulation generates trace files that can be visualized using tools like NAM for animations or X-Graph for graphical representations. This modular design allows users to simulate complex network behaviors with ease.

Figure 4.1 Basic Architecture of NS2

4.2 NAM Animation Tool

The Network Animator (NAM) is a Tcl/Tk-based tool used to visualize network simulations and analyze packet traces. It allows users to observe network topology, packet-level animations, and data flows. NAM was originally developed at LBL and later enhanced under the VINT project. By maintaining only essential information in memory and fetching additional data on-demand, NAM efficiently handles large-scale animation datasets. Trace files containing topology and packet trace information,

typically generated by NS2, are used as input for NAM visualizations

Figure 4.2 NAM Animation Tool

4.3 X-Graph

X-Graph is a charting utility included in the NS2 package, enabling users to create graphical representations of simulation results. By generating output files in Tcl scripts, users can visualize performance metrics such as energy consumption, packet delivery rates, and network lifetime. Figure 4.3 illustrates the use of X-Graph in plotting simulation data and analyzing traffic patterns for network performance.

Figure 4.3 Use X-Graph for Plotting Graphs in NS2

5 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1. RESULTS FOR THE FIRST PROPOSED ALGORITHM

5.1.1 Comparison of MAWCA and MOFGSA Protocols

This study evaluates the performance of MAWCA against the Multi-Objective Fractional Gravitational Search Algorithm (MOFGSA) in IoT networks. MAWCA optimizes CH selection based on node degree, cumulative operational time, mobility, and latency to enhance routing efficiency. Simulation results indicate that

MAWCA significantly improves packet delivery rate (PDR), network lifetime, and energy efficiency while reducing packet loss compared to MOFGSA.

To further enhance energy optimization, the study integrates the Energy-Aware and Secure Multi-Hop Routing (ESMR) protocol. ESMR organizes network nodes into hierarchical clusters using the k-nearest neighbors (k-NN) technique, ensuring efficient routing and balanced energy consumption. This hierarchical clustering enhances data transmission reliability and security by mitigating potential attacks.

Simulation results validate the effectiveness of MAWCA and ESMR, demonstrating superior performance in energy efficiency and network stability, making them well-suited for dynamic IoT environments.

5.1.2 Parameters Compared Graphically

1. Network Lifetime

The number of simulation rounds directly correlates with the network lifetime. Figure 5.1 illustrates that the proposed MAWCA + ESMR protocol achieves significantly higher longevity at 19,000 simulation rounds compared to MOFGSA's 13,000 rounds and EMEECP's 14,500 rounds. This gain is attributed to efficient energy consumption and optimal clustering strategies, which reduce redundant communication.

Figure 5.1 Comparison of Network Lifetime

2. Energy Consumption

Energy consumption over time is a critical parameter for WSNs. As shown in Figure 5.2, the proposed MAWCA protocol achieves superior energy efficiency by minimizing unnecessary transmissions and employing energy-aware routing strategies. This conservation results in prolonged network operation, outpacing both MOFGSA.

Figure 5.2 Energy consumption

3. Packet Delivery Rate (PDR)

PDR measures the success rate of data delivery across the network. Figure 5.3 demonstrates the proposed protocol's high reliability, with consistently higher PDR compared to existing protocols. This improvement stems from the robustness of MAWCA's clustering approach and the reliability of ESMR's secure multi-hop routing.

Figure 5.3 PDR

4. Packet Loss

Packet loss is a critical measure of network stability. Figure 5.4 highlights a substantial reduction in packet loss for the proposed method compared to MOFGSA and EMEECP. By optimizing routing paths and addressing node mobility effectively, the protocol minimizes disruptions caused by congestion and node failures.

Figure 5.4 Packet loss

The proposed MAWCA protocol is evaluated against recent clustering and routing algorithms, demonstrating superior performance in key metrics.

5.2 SECOND APPROACH OF THE PROPOSED WORK

COMPARISON OF MAWCA & CA-IOT PROTOCOLS

5.2.1 DATA COLLECTION NODE

Our Data Collection product, source nodes for Data Collection import survey data. With the use of this format, case data the actual answers to the inquiries acquired during a survey can be distinguished from the metadata, which explains how the case data was gathered and arranged. Information like question texts, variable names and descriptions, definitions for numerous response variables, translations of text strings, and case data structure definitions

make up metadata. Data collection may be used to assess the general condition of circumstances rather than just particular instances or incidents. It is feasible to gauge development and achievement when data is obtained, followed, and credibly examined over time (or lack thereof).

5.2.2 PARAMETERS COMPARED GRAPHICALLY

1. Network Lifetime

The x axis in this graph stands for the number of rounds, and the y axis represents lifetime. The difference between the values of the proposed and current systems, clearly demonstrates that the proposed method has a higher lifetime efficiency than the existing one.

Figure 5.1 Comparison of Network Lifetime

2. Energy Consumption

The energy utilized by the network is displayed in this graph. In this way, the x-axis represents the number of rounds, while the y-axis represents the energy acquired by the network. This graphical representation makes it very evident that our proposed approach uses less energy than the current system.

Figure 5.2 Energy consumption

3. Packet Delivery Rate (PDR)

The PDR measures how many data packets are actually received at the receiver end compared to how many were initially transmitted by the sender. An alternative definition would be one in which the number of nodes actually sent by the sender and received by the receiver are the same. According to this x-graph, this proposed work is more effective than the first proposed work.

Figure 5.3 PDR

4. Packet Loss

Packet losses refer to data packets that are misplaced while being transported across a network. Packet loss occurs when data packets are dropped during data transmission for a variety of causes, including network congestion, hardware issues, software flaws, and more. Graphical images show that the proposed system's packet loss is lower than that of the current system.

Figure 5.4 Packet loss

The proposed MAWCA protocol is evaluated against recent clustering and routing algorithms, demonstrating superior performance in key metrics.

6 CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This research presents two approaches to extend IoT network lifetime using wireless sensor networks. The first employs the Mobility-Aware Weighted Clustering Algorithm (MAWCA) with a secure multi-hop routing protocol to optimize cluster head (CH) selection and enhance energy efficiency. It uses shortest-path routing via reliable nodes and analyzes connection data to reduce congestion and retransmissions. The second approach introduces cloud-assisted IoT with randomly distributed data collection nodes to improve network lifespan, throughput, and energy efficiency. Clustering is guided by proximity, initial energy, and residual energy, with the cloud assigning CH election probabilities. Future work aims to further enhance WSN-based IoT efficiency and apply security techniques to address limitations.

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